

Kinetics of Oxidation of Thiocarbohydrazide, its Metal Complex and Hydrazone by Chloramine-T in partial Aqueous Media

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Kinetics of oxidations of thiocarbohydrazide (TCH), its metal complex and hydrazone by chloramine-T in 1 : 1 (v/v) water-methanol and water-acetic acid media have been investigated in the presence of perchloric acid. Oxidations of all the substrates in both the media showed first order kinetics in [oxidant] and varying fractional orders in [substrate]. Oxidation of TCH and its complex in water-methanol medium showed positive fractional order kinetics in $[H^+]$ while oxidations of hydrazone in water-methanol medium and those of both TCH and hydrazone in water-acetic acid medium showed inverse fractional order kinetics in $[H^+]$. Variation in ionic strength of the medium had little effect on the rates of oxidations, in all the cases. Variation in solvent composition of the medium had considerable effect on rates of oxidations, but the effect was more pronounced in water-acetic acid medium. Addition of the reduced product of the oxidant had no significant effect on the rates of reactions. Both two-pathway and Michaelis-Menten type mechanisms have been considered to explain the observed results and the related rate laws deduced. The rate-limiting steps have been identified in all the cases; the coefficients of these steps were calculated at different temperatures and the activation parameters computed. The rate constants have also been predicted from the rate laws as [substrate] and $[H^+]$ were varied. The results of the investigations have also been compared with those in aqueous medium.

THE chemistry of hydrazine and its derivatives is of interest due to their wide synthetic and analytical applications and biological activities^{1,2}. The chemical behaviour of thiocarbohydrazide is similar to its keto analogue carbohydrazide. Thiocarbohydrazide possesses anticarcinogenic and antibacterial properties. There are no reports on the mechanistic aspects of its reactions in solution. In continuation of our work on the mechanistic aspects of its reactions³, we report herein the kinetics of oxidations of thiocarbohydrazide in the free and metal-bound states and its hydrazone by *N*-chlorotoluene-*p*-sulphonamide (chloramine-T, CAT) in 1 : 1 (v/v) water-methanol and 1 : 1 (v/v) water-acetic acid media in the presence of perchloric acid.

Experimental

Chloramine-T (E. Merck) was purified and its stock solution ($\sim 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) prepared in double-distilled water was standardised by iodometric method.

Thiocarbohydrazide (TCH) was prepared by refluxing the mixture of carbondisulphide and hydrazine hydrate at 90° for a period of 1 h³. The resulting colourless crystals were recrystallised from water, m.p. 168°d . It was characterised by its ir spectrum and sulphur estimation. The complex, bis(thiocarbohydrazide)zinc(II) chloride

was obtained by mixing warm solutions of zinc chloride in dimethyl formamide-water (5 : 1, v/v) and thiocarbohydrazide in dimethylformamide, in an approximately 1 : 2 mole ratio. The resulting colourless crystals separated on standing for over 1 h, were washed with hydrochloric acid (0.10 mol dm^{-3}) and dried under reduced pressure over P_2O_5 .

The hydrazone, bis-ethylidinedithiocarbohydrazide was prepared⁴ by adding 50% excess of acetaldehyde in ethanol to a solution of thiocarbohydrazide in acetic acid (1 mol dm^{-3}) and refluxing the resulting mixture for 1 h. The pale yellow crystals that separated out were recrystallised from dimethylformamide, m.p. $\sim 245^\circ$. The hydrazone was further characterised by recording its ir spectrum and determining its sulphur content.

Stock solutions ($\sim 0.05 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) of thiocarbohydrazide, its metal complex and hydrazone were prepared in aqueous perchloric acid (0.10 mol dm^{-3}) as their aqueous solutions were unstable and decomposed on standing. The ionic strength of the reaction medium was maintained at 0.30 mol dm^{-3} employing concentrated aqueous sodium perchlorate (E. Merck) solution. All other reagents used were of accepted grades of purity.

Kinetic measurements: The kinetic studies were made in glass-stoppered reagent bottles under pseudo-first order conditions with [substrate] (TCH or its metal complex or hydrazone) \gg [oxidant]

(5–30 fold excess). The reactions were initiated by the rapid addition of the requisite amounts of oxidant solution (thermally pre-equilibrated at a desired temperature) to solutions containing known amounts of the substrate, perchloric acid, sodium perchlorate and water (and methanol or acetic acid to maintain 1 : 1, v/v solvent composition), thermostated at the same temperature. The progress of the reactions was monitored at least for two half-lives by the iodometric estimation of unreacted oxidant at regular time intervals. The pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) were computed by the graphical methods and the values were reproducible within $\pm 4\%$ error.

Stoichiometry and product analysis: The stoichiometries of TCH-CAT reactions in the free and metal-bound states and hydrazone-CAT reaction were determined by allowing the reactions to go to completion at 303 K and at different $[HClO_4]$ (0.02–0.20 mol dm⁻³) and [substrate]/[oxidant] ratios. The presence of sulphate and CO₂ in the reaction products were detected by standard tests⁵. Sulphate was estimated gravimetrically⁶, yields $84 \pm 5\%$ Toluene-*p*-sulphonamide (TSA), the reduced product of the oxidant, was detected by paper chromatography employing benzyl alcohol saturated with water as the solvent and 0.5% vanillin in 1% HCl solution in ether as the spray reagent ($R_f=0.91$). The observed stoichiometry per mole of TCH in the free and metal-bound states and thiocarbohydrazone may be represented by equations (1) and (2).

where $Ar=CH_3C_6H_4$

Results and Discussion

The kinetics of oxidations of thiocarbohydrazone (TCH), its metal complex $Zn(TCH)_2Cl_2$ and hydrazone by chloramine-T in 1 : 1 (v/v) water-methanol and water-acetic acid media in the presence of perchloric acid were investigated at several initial concentrations of the reactants and $HClO_4$. The results of these studies are shown in Tables 1–4 and Figs. 1–5.

Oxidations in water-methanol medium: At fixed [substrate] (several fold excess over the [oxidant]) and $[H^+]$, the plots of $\log ([CAT]_0/[CAT])$ vs time were linear for at least two half-lives for oxidations of all the substrates. The pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) calculated from the plots were insensitive to the variations in $[oxidant]_0$ (Table 1) establishing first order kinetics in $[oxidant]_0$ for all the oxidations. At constant $[oxidant]_0$ and $[HClO_4]$, the rates increased with increase in [substrate]. The plots of $\log k_{obs}$ vs $\log [TCH]$, $\log [complex]$ and $\log [hydrazone]$ gave

TABLE 1 – PSEUDO FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANTS (k_{obs}) FOR OXIDATION OF THIOCARBOHYDRAZIDE (TCH), $Zn(TCH)_2Cl_2$ COMPLEX AND HYDRAZONE BIS-ETHYLIDINETHIOCARBOHYDRAZIDE BY CHLORAMINE-T

Medium : 1 : 1 (v/v) water-methanol, temp. = 283 K, $I = 0.30$ mol dm⁻³

$[CAT]_0$ $\times 10^3$ mol dm ⁻³	$[substrate]_0$ $\times 10^3$ mol dm ⁻³	$[HClO_4]$ $\times 10$ mol dm ⁻³	$k_{obs} (\times 10^4 s^{-1})$		
			TCH	Complex	Hydrazone
Effect of varying $[CAT]_0$					
0.25	1.0	1.0	6.2	9.8	–
0.5	1.0	1.0	6.1	9.8	7.9
1.0	1.0	1.0	6.1	9.9	7.9
2.0	1.0	1.0	6.0	9.9	8.0
3.0	1.0	1.0	–	–	7.9
Effect of varying $[substrate]_0$					
1.0	0.5	1.0	3.5	5.5	6.7
1.0	1.0	1.0	6.1	9.9	7.9
1.0	1.5	1.0	–	11.8	8.7
1.0	2.0	1.0	9.6	14.5	9.9
1.0	3.0	1.0	12.2	–	–
Effect of varying $[HClO_4]$					
1.0	1.0	0.2	4.4	5.0	20.2
1.0	1.0	0.5	5.4	6.4	13.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	6.1	9.9	7.9
1.0	1.0	2.0	7.9	13.0	4.9

TABLE 2—PSEUDO-FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANTS (k_{obs}) FOR OXIDATION OF THIOCARBOHYDRAZIDE (TCH) AND ITS HYDRAZONE BY CHLORAMINE-T

 Medium : water-acetic acid, temp. = 293 K, $I = 0.30 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

$[\text{CAT}]_0$ $\times 10^3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$	$[\text{substrate}]_0$ $\times 10^3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$	$[\text{HClO}_4]$ $\times 10 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$	$k_{\text{obs}} (\times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1})$	
			TCH	Hydrazone
Effect of varying $[\text{CAT}]_0$				
0.5	1.0	1.0	8.9	10.1
1.0	1.0	1.0	9.0	10.3
2.0	1.0	1.0	9.0	10.3
3.0	1.0	1.0	9.0	10.2
Effect of varying $[\text{substrate}]_0$				
1.0	0.5	1.0	6.2	9.4
1.0	1.0	1.0	9.0	10.3
1.0	1.5	1.0	—	11.5
1.0	2.0	1.0	13.6	12.4
1.0	3.0	1.0	17.2	—
Effect of varying $[\text{HClO}_4]$				
1.0	1.0	0.3	22.3	23.0
1.0	1.0	0.5	16.5	17.9
1.0	1.0	1.0	9.0	10.3
1.0	1.0	2.0	5.5	6.3

 TABLE 3 EFFECT OF VARYING IONIC STRENGTH (I) AND DIELECTRIC CONSTANT OF REACTION MEDIUM AND ADDITION OF REACTION PRODUCT TOLUENE-*p*-SULPHONAMIDE (TSA) ON THE RATE OF OXIDATION OF THIOCARBOHYDRAZIDE (TCH), ITS METAL COMPLEX AND HYDRAZONE BY CHLORAMINE-T*

Medium : 1 : 1 (v/v) water-methanol, (temp. = 283 K) and water-acetic acid (temp. = 293 K)

I mol dm^{-3}	$k_{\text{obs}} (\times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1})$ in 1 : 1 (v/v) medium				
	Water-methanol			Water-acetic acid	
	TCH	Complex	Hydrazone	TCH	Hydrazone
0.2	5.5	9.1	8.8	10.0	11.7
0.3	6.1	9.9	7.9	9.0	10.3
0.5	6.6	11.6	7.1	8.1	9.3
	[TSA] ($\times 10^3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$)				
1.0	6.1	9.9	7.9	9.0	10.2
2.0	6.2	9.9	7.9	9.0	10.3
4.0	6.1	9.8	7.9	9.0	10.3
	MeOH or HOAc (%)				
30	6.4	13.4	6.8	18.7	17.4
40	6.2	10.6	7.4	13.3	13.3
50	6.1	9.9	7.9	9.0	10.3
60	5.7	8.8	9.5	6.3	9.0

* $10^3 [\text{CAT}]_0 = 10^3 [\text{TCH}]_0 = 10 [\text{HClO}_4] = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $I = 0.3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ while making other variations.

 TABLE 4—KINETIC DATA AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR OXIDATION OF THIOCARBOHYDRAZIDE (TCH), $\text{Zn}(\text{TCH})_2\text{Cl}_2$ COMPLEX AND HYDRAZONE BY CHLORAMINE T

Medium : 1 : 1 (v/v) water-methanol and water-acetic acid media

Orders observed	TCH	Complex	Hydrazone
1 : 1 (v/v) water-methanol medium			
[CAT]	1.0	1.0	1.0
[substrate]	0.73	0.70	0.30
[H ⁺]	0.25	0.42	-0.65
1 : 1 (v/v) water-acetic acid medium			
[CAT]	1.0	—	1.0
[substrate]	0.57	—	0.22
[H ⁺]	-0.74	—	-0.66
Aqueous medium			
[CAT]	1.0	1.0	1.9
[substrate]	0.6	0.6	0.7
[H ⁺]	0.4	0.5	-0.4

 Activation parameters^a in 1 : 1 (v/v) water-methanol medium

E_a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	39.9(56.8)	36.9(42.4)	68.6(102)
log A	4.1 (7.3)	3.8 (4.8)	9.6(15.8)
ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	38.9(50.7)	35.2(37.8)	67.9(93.2)
ΔS^\ddagger (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-121.8	-131.1	-17.1
	(-80.1)	(-121.5)	(74.5)
ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	73.4(73.2)	72.2(72.4)	72.7(114.5)

^a Activation parameters were calculated for both the Michaelis-Menten type and two-pathway mechanisms; values in parentheses are for two-pathway mechanism.

straight lines with slopes less than unity (Table 4). The plots of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[\text{S}]$ gave better correlations than k_{obs} vs $[\text{S}]$ plots (Figs. 1 and 2). At fixed [oxidant] and [substrate], the rates increased with increase in $[\text{H}^+]$ for TCH and complex oxidations

TABLE 5 - COMPARISON OF PREDICTED AND EXPERIMENTAL RATE CONSTANTS FOR OXIDATION OF THIOCARBOHYDRAZIDE (TCH) AND ITS METAL COMPLEX BY CHLORAMINE-T

Medium : 1 : 1 (v/v) water-methanol

[substrate] ($\times 10^3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$)	$k (\times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1})$					
	TCH		Complex			
	Predicted ^a I	Obsd. II	Predicted ^a I	Obsd. II	Predicted ^a II	Obsd.
0.50	3.9	4.0	3.5	6.5	6.5	5.5
1.0	6.0	6.0	6.0	8.7	8.5	9.9
1.5	-	-	-	10.9	9.6	11.8
2.0	10.2	9.2	9.6	13.1	14.3	14.5
3.0	14.4	11.8	12.2	-	-	-
[H ⁺] ($\times 10^3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$)						
2.0	4.5	4.5	4.4	6.7	4.5	5.0
4.0	4.9	5.1	5.4	7.4	5.8	6.4
10.0	5.7	6.0	6.0	8.6	8.5	9.9
20.0	7.3	7.8	7.9	10.9	12.4	13.0

^aThe values predicted from the rate law 17(I) and rate law 20(II).

Fig. 1. Plots of (a) k_{obs} vs [TCH] and (b) k_{obs} vs [complex]; $10^3[\text{CAT}]_0 = 10[\text{H}^+] = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $I = 0.3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, temp. = 283 K, medium : 1 : 1 (v/v) water-methanol.

Fig. 2. Plots of (a) $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[\text{TCH}]$ and (b) $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[\text{complex}]$; $10^3[\text{CAT}]_0 = 10[\text{H}^+] = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $I = 0.30 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, temp. = 283 K, medium : 1 : 1 (v/v) water-methanol.

with fractional order kinetics in $[\text{H}^+]$, while the rate decreased with increase in $[\text{H}^+]$ for hydrazone oxidation with an inverse fractional order kinetics in $[\text{H}^+]$ (Table 1). Variation in ionic strength of the medium or addition of the reduced product of the oxidant had little or negligible effects on the rates of oxidations (Table 3). Increase in methanol composition of the solvent slightly decreased the rate for TCH and complex oxidations while increased in the case of hydrazone oxidation.

Further, the substrate concentration was varied at different temperatures and the coefficients of the rate-limiting steps have been calculated at each temperature as described under discussion. The latter constants were employed to compute the activation parameters (Table 4).

Oxidations in water-acetic acid medium: At constant [substrate] and $[\text{H}^+]$, the first order plots were linear for at least two half-lives, even under these conditions. The pseudo-first order rate constants computed from the plots, were unaffected by the variation in [oxidant] (Table 2). The rates increased with increase in either [TCH] or [hydrazone] with fractional order kinetics in each case (Table 4), while the rates decreased with increase in $[\text{H}^+]$ with inverse fractional order kinetics in $[\text{H}^+]$ for both the oxidations. Further the plots of $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[\text{S}]$ and $1/k_{obs}$ vs $[\text{H}^+]$ were linear in both the cases (Figs. 3 and 4).

Fig 3 (a) Plots of k_{obs} vs $[H^+]$; $10^3 [CAT]_0 = 10^3 [substrate]_0 = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $I = 0.30 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, temp = 283 K, medium : 1 : 1 (v/v) water-methanol; (○) TCH and (□) complex (b) Plots of $1/k_{obs}$ vs $[H^+]$, $10^3 [CAT]_0 = 10^3 [substrate]_0 = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $I = 0.30 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. (○) TCH, (▽) hydrazone ($H_2O - MeOH$) and (□) hydrazone ($H_2O - HOAc$)

The rates slightly decreased with the increase in ionic strength of the medium but the addition of the reaction product of the oxidant had no effect on the rates of both the oxidations (Table 3). Increase in acetic acid composition of the solvent decreased the rates of oxidations.

Mechanisms of oxidations :

Chloramine-T (*N*-chloro-*N*-sodiotoluene-*p* sulphonamide, $ArSO_2NClNa$, where $Ar = C_6H_4CH_3$) is fairly a strong electrolyte in aqueous solutions⁷. It furnishes different types of reactive species in aqueous and partial aqueous solutions depending upon pH of the medium, due to the presence of following equilibria,

Fig 4 Plots of (a) k_{obs} vs $[substrate]_0$ and (b) $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[substrate]$; $10^3 [CAT]_0 = 10^3 [substrate]_0 = 1.0 [H^+] = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $I = 0.30 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; (○) TCH (▽) hydrazone ($H_2O - MeOH$) and (□) hydrazone ($H_2O - HOAc$)

Thus the possible oxidising species in acid solution of CAT are $ArSO_2NCl^-$, $ArSO_2NHCl$, $HOCl$ and $ArSO_2NCl_2$ at low $[H^+]$ and $ArSO_2NH_2Cl^+$ and H_2OCl^+ at high acidities.

Oxidation in 1 : 1 (v/v) water-methanol medium :

TCH and its metal complex : The observed kinetics for the oxidation of TCH and its metal complex (Table 4) under these conditions may be explained by a Michaelis-Menten type mechanism (Scheme 1).

where, S (substrate) is TCH or its metal complex

Scheme 1

Fig. 5 (a) Plots of $\log k_{obs}$ vs % MeOH; $10^3 [CAT]_0 = 10^3 [substrate]_0 = 10 [H^+] = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $I = 0.30 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, temp = 283 K: (O) TCH, (□) complex and (Δ) hydrazone (b) Plots of $\log k_{obs}$ vs % HOAc; $10^3 [CAT]_0 = 10^3 [substrate]_0 = 10 [H^+] = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $I = 0.30 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, temp = 283 K: (O) TCH and (□) hydrazone

The rate law based on Scheme 1 has been deduced as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
 [CAT]_{tot} &= [ArSO_2NHCl] + [ArSO_2NH_2Cl^+] + [X] \\
 &= \frac{[ArSO_2NH_2Cl^+]}{K_1[H^+]} + [ArSO_2NH_2Cl^+] + [X] \\
 &= \frac{1 + K_1[H^+]}{K_1[H^+]} \frac{[X]}{K_2[S]} + [X] \\
 &= \frac{1 + K_1[H^+] + K_1K_2[H^+][S]}{K_1K_2[H^+][S]} [X] \\
 [X] &= \frac{K_1K_2[CAT]_t[S][H^+]}{1 + K_1[H^+] + K_1K_2[S][H^+]} \quad (10)
 \end{aligned}$$

The rate of reaction is given by equation (11),

$$-\frac{d[CAT]}{dt} = k_3[X] \quad (11)$$

Substituting for [X], we have,

$$-\frac{d[CAT]}{dt} = \frac{K_1K_2k_3[CAT]_t[S][H^+]}{1 + K_1[H^+] + K_1K_2[S][H^+]} \quad (12)$$

Equation (12) can be rearranged as

$$-\frac{1}{[CAT]} \frac{d[CAT]_t}{dt} = \frac{K_1K_2k_3[S][H^+]}{1 + K_1[H^+] + K_1K_2[S][H^+]} \quad (13)$$

If now an assumption is made that

$$-\frac{1}{[CAT]_t} \frac{d[CAT]}{dt} \approx -\frac{d \ln [CAT]}{dt} = k_{obs}$$

then equation (13) takes the form,

$$k_{obs} = \frac{K_1K_2k_3[S][H^+]}{1 + K_1[H^+] + K_1K_2[S][H^+]} \quad (14)$$

or

$$\frac{1}{k_{obs}} = \left\{ \frac{1 + K_1[H^+]}{K_1K_2k_3[H^+]} \right\} \frac{1}{[S]} + \frac{1}{k_3} \quad (15)$$

The plots of $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[S]$ were linear with finite intercepts for the oxidation of both TCH and its metal complex (Fig. 2) in accordance with rate law (15). Reciprocals of the intercepts gave values for k_3 , the constant of the rate-limiting step. Further, the substrate concentrations were varied at different temperatures (278–293 K) and the values for k_3 were calculated at each temperature. The latter constants were employed to compute the activation parameters for both the oxidations.

Although the above mechanism explains the observed results quite satisfactorily, the deduced rate law cannot predict the observed linearity between k_{obs} and $[H^+]$ (Fig. 3). Further, the double reciprocal plots ($1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[H^+]$) were non-linear. Hence the same results can be explained by a two-pathway mechanism (Schemes 2 and 3) instead of Michaelis-Menten type mechanism. This is further supported by the fact that the direct plots k_{obs} vs $[S]$, were reasonably linear for both the oxidations (Table 1). It is also reasonable to presume that Cl^+ transfer from $ArSO_2NH_2Cl^+$ to S takes place in a fast step when compared to similar transfer from $ArSO_2NHCl$. Hence the two competitive schemes are

Scheme 2

Scheme 3

The related combined rate law is given by equation (16),

$$-\frac{d[CAT]}{dt} = k_4[CAT][H^+] + k_5[CAT][S] \quad (16)$$

or

$$k_{obs} = k_4[H^+] + k_5[S] \quad (17)$$

The rate law (17) is in accordance with the observed linearities between k_{obs} and $[\text{H}^+]$ or $[\text{S}]$ for the oxidations of both TCH and its metal complex (Figs. 1 and 3a). Further, two sets of k_4 and k_5 were calculated from the slopes and intercepts of the plots, k_{obs} vs $[\text{H}^+]$ and k_{obs} vs $[\text{S}]$. The values predicted from one plot were used to predict the rate constants as the other concentration was varied and vice-versa. The predicted values compared with the observed constants are shown in Table 5. As can be seen, there is an excellent agreement between the two sets of values. Further, k_5 values were computed at different temperatures and these constants were also used to calculate the activation parameters.

Although two-pathway mechanism explains reasonably well the observed kinetics for the oxidations of TCH and its metal complex, the double reciprocal plots ($1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[\text{S}]$) gave better correlation than the direct plots as the substrate concentrations were varied (Figs. 1 and 2). This made us to conclude that the Michaelis-Menten type mechanism gives a better fit than the two-pathway mechanism. But as already been pointed out, the related rate law cannot explain the observed linearity between k_{obs} and $[\text{H}^+]$ for both the oxidations. Hence a combination of Michaelis-Menten type and two-pathway mechanism (Scheme 2 and modified Scheme 3) may give a better fit than either of the two (Schemes 2 and 4).

Based on Scheme 4, rate law (18) has been deduced,

$$-\frac{d[\text{CAT}]}{dt} = \frac{K_5 k_6 [\text{C}][\text{T}]_0 [\text{S}]}{1 + K_5 [\text{S}]} \quad (18)$$

or

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{K_5 k_6 [\text{S}]}{1 + K_5 [\text{S}]} \quad (19)$$

The combined rate law (20) accounts for the observed results,

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{K_5 k_6 [\text{S}]}{1 + K_5 [\text{S}]} + k_4 [\text{H}^+] \quad (20)$$

The slope of the plot, k_{obs} vs $[\text{H}^+]$ (Fig. 3a) gave k_4 ($10^3 k_4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1} = 1.8$ TCH) and 4.3 (complex)).

Equation (20) may be rearranged as

$$k_{\text{obs}} - k_4 [\text{H}^+] = \frac{K_5 k_6 [\text{S}]}{1 + K_5 [\text{S}]}$$

or

$$\frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}} - k_4 [\text{H}^+]} = \frac{1}{K_5 k_6 [\text{S}]} + \frac{1}{k_6} \quad (21)$$

The plots of $1/(k_{\text{obs}} - k_4 [\text{H}^+])$ vs $1/[\text{S}]$ were linear in accordance with equation (21) (Fig. 6a). From the slopes and intercepts of the plots, the constants k_6 and K_5 were calculated for the oxidations of both TCH and its metal complex: $k_6 \times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1} = 3.1$ (TCH) and 1.0 (complex); $K_5 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} = 15.6$ (TCH) and 56.4 (complex). The latter values along with k_4 values were employed to predict the rate constants for $[\text{S}]$ and $[\text{H}^+]$ variations in both the cases. The predicted values compared with the experimental constants are shown in Table 5. As can be seen, agreement between the predicted values and the experimental constants is much better than those predicted from the simple two-pathway mechanism. This may suggest that the two competitive schemes include a Michaelis-Menten type mechanism.

Fig. 6. (a) Plots of $1/(k_{\text{obs}} - k_4 [\text{H}^+])$ vs $1/[\text{substrate}]$ (see equation 21): (O) TCH and (Δ) complex. (b) Plots of $1/(k_{\text{obs}} - k_5 [\text{S}])$ vs $[\text{H}^+]$ (see equation 31): (\square) hydrazone ($\text{H}_2\text{O} - \text{MeOH}$) and (\bullet) hydrazone ($\text{H}_2\text{O} - \text{HOAc}$).

Oxidation of thiocarbohydrazide: The conversion of thiocarbohydrazide into its hydrazone changed its kinetics significantly. The rate dependence on $[\text{H}^+]$ was changed from fractional order to inverse fractional order. The observed results for hydrazone oxidation (Table 4) may be explained by either Scheme 5 or Scheme 6. In Scheme 5, deprotonation of oxidant takes place in a pre-equilibrium step before attacking the substrate whereas in Scheme 6 deprotonation takes

place in the course of interaction,

Scheme 5

where, S is hydrazone. Based on Scheme 5, rate laws (22–25) have been deduced.

$$-\frac{d[\text{CAT}]}{dt} = \frac{K_7 K_8 k_9 [\text{CAT}]_0 [\text{S}]}{K_7 + [\text{H}^+] + K_8 [\text{S}] [\text{H}^+] + K_7 K_8 [\text{S}]} \quad (22)$$

or

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{K_7 K_8 k_9 [\text{S}]}{K_7 + [\text{H}^+] + K_8 [\text{S}] [\text{H}^+] + K_7 K_8 [\text{S}]} \quad (23)$$

or

$$\frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{K_7 + [\text{H}^+]}{K_7 K_8 k_9} \frac{1}{[\text{S}]} + \frac{K_7 + [\text{H}^+]}{K_7 k_9} \quad (24)$$

or

$$\frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{1 + K_8 [\text{S}]}{K_7 K_8 k_9 [\text{S}]} [\text{H}^+] + \frac{1 + K_8 [\text{S}]}{K_8 k_9 [\text{S}]} \quad (25)$$

The rate laws (24) and (25) predict linearities between $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ and $1/[\text{S}]$ and $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ and $[\text{H}^+]$. The plots were linear (Figs. 3 and 4) in conformity with the predictions. The ratio of intercept to slope of the plots $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $[\text{H}^+]$ and $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[\text{S}]$ gave equilibrium constants K_7 and K_8 respectively: $K_7 = 0.038 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $K_8 = 200 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$. Then the rate constant k_9 was calculated from the intercept of either the former or the latter plot,

$k_9 = 4.57 \times 10^{-8} \text{ s}^{-1}$. These computed constants K_7 , K_8 and k_9 were used to predict the rate constants as $[\text{S}]$ and $[\text{H}^+]$ were varied. Comparison of the predicted values with the experimental constants (Table 6) shows a good agreement between the two sets of values, thus confirming the consistency of the rate law.

Scheme 6

The related rate laws are

$$-\frac{d[\text{CAT}]}{dt} = \frac{K_{10} k_{11} [\text{CAT}]_0 [\text{S}]}{[\text{H}^+] + K_{10} [\text{S}]} \quad (26)$$

or

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{K_{10} k_{11} [\text{S}]}{[\text{H}^+] + K_{10} [\text{S}]} \quad (27)$$

or

$$\frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{K_{10} k_{11}} \frac{1}{[\text{S}]} + \frac{1}{k_{11}} \quad (28)$$

Two sets of values for constants K_{10} and k_{11} were calculated from the plots of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[\text{S}]$ and $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $[\text{H}^+]$ (Figs. 3 and 4). The values computed from one plot were used to predict the rate constants from the rate laws for the variation of other and vice versa. A good agreement between the predicted rate constants and experimental values may indicate that step (i) of Scheme 6 (combination of steps (i) and (ii) of Scheme 5) can as well serve the purpose.

TABLE 6 - COMPARISON OF PREDICTED AND EXPERIMENTAL RATE CONSTANTS FOR OXIDATION OF THIOCARBOHYDRAZIDE AND ITS HYDRAZONE BY CHLORAMINE-T IN 1 : 1 (V/V) WATER-ACETIC ACID MEDIUM AND HYDRAZONE IN WATER-METHANOL MEDIUM

[substrate] ($\times 10^4 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$)	$k (\times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1})$											
	TCH ($\text{H}_2\text{O} - \text{HOAc}$)			Hydrazone ($\text{H}_2\text{O} - \text{HOAc}$)				Hydrazone ($\text{H}_2\text{O} - \text{MeOH}$)				
	Predicted ^a		Obsd.	Predicted ^a		Obsd.	Predicted ^a		Obsd.	Obsd.		
	I	II		I	II	III		I	II	III		
0.50	5.6	5.7	6.2	6.4	6.3	6.7	6.7	9.0	9.1	9.2	9.4	
1.0	9.1	9.5	9.0	8.2	8.2	7.7	7.9	10.8	10.8	10.3	10.3	
1.5	—	—	—	9.3	9.1	8.7	8.7	11.5	11.5	11.3	11.5	
2.0	13.6	15.1	13.6	9.9	10.0	9.6	9.9	12.4	12.0	12.4	12.4	
3.0	16.5	18.1	17.2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	
[H ⁺] ($\times 10^4 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$)												
2.0	—	—	—	20.2	20.1	27.9	20.2	—	—	—	—	
3.0	19.8	19.2	22.3	—	—	—	—	23.7	23.9	24.9	23.0	
5.0	15.6	15.3	16.5	13.1	13.2	13.2	13.0	17.8	17.8	17.2	17.9	
10.0	9.3	9.1	9.0	8.4	8.7	7.7	7.9	10.3	10.8	10.3	10.3	
20.0	5.5	5.5	5.5	4.8	4.9	4.9	4.9	6.3	6.1	6.4	6.3	

^aValues predicted from rate law 24 or 25(I), rate law 28(II) and rate law (30) (III).

The direct plot, k_{obs} vs $[S]$ is also linear in addition to the above plots (Fig. 4). Hence two-pathway mechanism can also be considered for explaining the observed kinetics

The related combined rate law is

$$-\frac{d[\text{CAT}]}{dt} = \frac{K_7 k_{1s} [\text{CAT}] [\text{H}_2\text{O}]}{K_7 + [\text{H}^+]} + k'_{1s} [\text{S}] [\text{CAT}] \quad (29)$$

or

$$k_{obs} = \frac{K_7 k_{1s} [\text{H}_2\text{O}]}{K_7 + [\text{H}^+]} + K_{1s} [\text{S}] \quad (30)$$

or

$$\frac{1}{k_{obs} - k'_{1s} [\text{S}]} = \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{K_7 k'_{1s}} + \frac{1}{k'_{1s}} \quad (31)$$

where, $k'_{1s} = K_{1s} [\text{H}_2\text{O}]$.

The slope of k_{obs} vs $[S]$ plot gave K_{1s} (Fig. 4). The plot of $1/(k_{obs} - k'_{1s} [S])$ vs $[\text{H}^+]$ was linear (Fig. 6) in accordance with the rate law (31). From the slope and intercept of the plot, the constants K_7 and k'_{1s} were calculated. These constants along with k_{1s} were employed to predict the rate constants from the rate law (30), for both the variation of $[S]$ and $[\text{H}^+]$. The predicted values are compared in Table 6. As can be seen there is a reasonable agreement between the two sets of values

where, Ar = $\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$

Although both two-pathway and Michaelis-Menten type mechanisms explain the observed

where, Ar = $\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$

results quite satisfactorily the latter mechanism seems to have an edge over the former.

Oxidations in 1:1 (v/v) water-acetic acid medium: Oxidations of both thiocarbohydrazide and its hydrazone under these conditions show similar trend (Table 4) unlike in water-methanol medium. They differ only in the magnitude of the kinetic orders. These results may also be explained by either Scheme 5 or Scheme 6. The rate dependence on $[H^+]$ for the oxidation of TCH is different in water-methanol and water-acetic acid media. It showed fractional order kinetics in $[H^+]$ in the former medium and inverse fractional in the latter.

Typical detailed mechanisms of oxidations are shown in Schemes 9 and 10.

Effect of solvent on the rates of ion-ion, ion-dipolar molecule and dipolar molecule-dipolar molecule reactions have been described in well-known monographs⁸⁻¹¹. The observed positive and negative dielectric effects in the present investigations may be explained by Amis⁸ and other concepts^{9,11}.

Comparisons and conclusions :

Comparison of kinetic data for the oxidations of thiocarbohydrazide, its metal complex and hydrazone in 1:1 (v/v) water-methanol and water-acetic acid media with those for oxidations in aqueous medium (Table 4) revealed that the change of medium from aqueous to water-methanol

medium generally had little effect on the kinetic trends and orders (Table 4). But the change of medium to aqueous acetic acid had reversed the rate dependence on $[H^+]$ from fractional to inverse fractional order for the oxidation of thiocarbohydrazide, probably indicating the change of reaction site on change of medium.

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